

A STUDY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE ANXIETY IN LEARNING ENGLISH OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF KOLHAPUR DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

In the present study an attempt has been made to identify extent of language Anxiety among the students of IX in learning English language. The data was collected using a language Anxiety scale. It was concluded that with the help of study extent of language Anxiety was measured among the secondary school students in very various talukas in Kolhapur district. The outcome of study may have valuable implications for the English teachers and may be helpful for those who are interested in devising novel teaching-learning process of English language.

Introduction

We are living in the 'age of anxiety'. Anxiety is the general feeling that all is not well. This state of helpless apprehension may be restricted to a limited number of environmental settings or it may be generalized to all in a form that has been described as "free floating anxiety". In the modern society it is not possible to prevent the development of certain minimum level of anxiety.

Almost every student feels nervous when he learns a new language particularly, our students are more anxious while learning English language. Anxiety is the most crucial facts which affects the English language learning. The principle concern in child guidance is not the abolition of all anxiety producing circumstances, but the elimination of needless anxieties wherever necessary.

A school going child faces many problems in learning, particularly in learning a second language. English being a foreign language and introduces as a third language in India, poses many problems to the learners in the process of learning it. As it is a new and particular language, the children face difficulties in learning the pronunciation, sentence

structure, grammar, vocabulary and other aspects of English language. Regional tongue interference is the main problem for the children. It becomes very difficult for them to acquire the four skills of language i.e. Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing and communication skill. The students whose medium of instruction is the regional language will be more anxious than the others, in learning English language.

Need of the study

For many years, English teachers are being penalized for the low standard of English attained by their pupils. The complaints are continued by employers against the school level and by University teachers against the students who take admission to the courses in Universities. A return to the teaching of English grammar is strongly advocated on all sides. But the controversy of grammar teaching is confused by ignorance, prejudice and contradictory opinions and there are at least fine pieces of evidence from the past, which show that the nature of the controversy has not changed very much in the last five decades. The reasons for this low standard of English may be the inconsistency in practice and the uncertainty about the stage where grammar should be taught. Most of the teachers teach grammar but the amount and the thoroughness depend largely on the personal conviction of the teachers as to its value. The condition of English in the schools where the medium of instruction is the regional language is chaotic. Many English teachers insist that the rudiments should be taught in the junior level. But in some junior level schools, there is no grammar teaching. Some teachers think that the groundwork should be covered in the first two years of schooling; others think that it should be special over the first four years. There are conflicting opinions even among teachers of English as to the value of grammar. It is maintained that training in grammar is helpful to the pupils to acquire English language; that it affords a sound discipline in logical thinking. A sound knowledge of grammatical rules is essential at least to speak and write correctly.

Significance of the study

The investigator is expected to diagnose the errors in learning of English by his students and developed teaching programme for reducing English language anxiety among the 9th standards students.

The researcher thinks that the study is significant because it is useful in reducing English language anxiety in various ways as given below:

- 1) It will be useful to teachers to know level of anxiety among secondary school students about learning of English language.
- 2) It will help the teachers to understand the causes of anxiety of learning English language.
- 3) The research will help to teachers to use various strategies and remedies for reducing the anxiety of students.

Scope of the Study

- 1) The study includes IX standard Marathi medium schools.
- 2) The study includes Girls and Boys of IX standard students.
- 3) The study includes Secondary schools of Urban and Rural areas in Kolhapur district.
- 4) The study includes IX standard English subject teaching learning process.

Delimitations of the Study

- 1) The study is limited to Marathi medium secondary school students.
- 2) The survey of Research was limited to 6 Talukas in Kolhapur District viz., Gadhinglaj, Ajara, Kagal, Karveer, Budhargad and Chandgad.
- 3) The study is limited to IX standard students of English subject teaching learning process programme.
- 4) The study is limited to IX standard students anxiety in English language only.
- 5) The study is confined to English subject teachers of Kolhapur district only.

Objectives of the Study

To find out the English language anxiety level of IX standard students.

Research Questions:-

What is the extent of language Anxiety among the IX standard students.

Assumptions of the Study

Following are the assumptions of the present study:

1. IX standard students have English language anxiety.
2. Due to English language anxiety the students commits errors in English grammar, vocabulary and sentence pattern.

Research Hypotheses of the Study

There is relation between English language anxiety and error in English grammar, vocabulary and sentence pattern.

Methodology and data collection:-

In the present study an attempt has been made to investigate the nature of anxiety of English language IX various talukas in kolhapur district

Sampling:-

Population study is all IX std. student Marathi medium schools in all over Maharashtra. The talukas were selected by simple random techniques and sample of IX standard students and teachers were selected by purposively. Thus 1200 students of IX std. were selected for the study.

Method Used in the Study

The present research is descriptive research in which survey method is used.

Data Presentation and analysis:

Association between Levels of Anxiety with Different Characteristics

Factors	Low level of anxiety	%	Medium level of anxiety	%	High level of anxiety	%	Total
Taluks							
Ajara	32	16.00	105	52.50	63	31.50	200
Budarghad	84	42.00	84	42.00	32	16.00	200
Chandgad	39	19.50	110	55.00	51	25.50	200
Gadahinglaj	42	21.00	109	54.50	49	24.50	200
Kagal	71	35.50	84	42.00	45	22.50	200
Karaveer	48	24.00	93	46.50	59	29.50	200
Chi-square=58.7923 df=10 p=0.00000, S							
Gender							
Male	190	31.67	287	47.83	123	20.50	600
Female	126	21.00	298	49.67	176	29.33	600
Chi-square=22.5642 df=2 p=0.00001, S							
Location							
Rural	159	26.50	305	50.83	136	22.67	600
Urban	157	26.17	280	46.67	163	27.17	600
Chi-square=3.5191 df=2 p=0.17213							
Total	316	26.33	585	48.75	299	24.92	1200

Interpretation:

From the results of the above table, it can be observed that,

1. Out of a total of 1200 students of 9th standard, in which 48.75% of students have medium level of anxiety, 26.33% students have low anxiety and 24.92% of students have higher level of anxiety towards English language. In which, a maximum of 42.00% of students of Budarghad taluk have low anxiety level as compared to a minimum of 16.00% of students of Ajara taluk followed by other talukas students. However, maximum of 55.00% of students of Chandgad taluk have medium level of anxiety and minimum of 42.00% of students of Kagal taluk have medium of anxiety level followed by other talukas. Similarly, maximum of 29.50% of students of Karaveer taluk have high level of anxiety and minimum of 16.00% of students of Budarghad taluk have high of anxiety level followed by other talukas. But, chi-square test of significance clearly showed that, a significant differences was observed between different taluka places with different anxiety levels of students of 9th standard towards English language (Chi-square=58.7923, $p < 0.05$) at 5% level of significance.
2. A maximum and significant higher of 49.67% of female 9th standard students have medium level of anxiety towards English language as compared to 47.83% of boy students. However, 29.33% of girl students have high level of anxiety towards English language followed by only 20.50% of boy students. Similarly, 31.67% of girl students have low level of anxiety towards English language followed by only 21.00% of boy students. But, a significant difference or association was observed between different levels of anxiety and gender of students of 9th standard towards English language (Chi-square=22.5642, $p < 0.05$) at 5% level of significance.
3. It clearly showed that, the rural and urban secondary school 9th standard students have similar percentage of low, medium and high levels of anxiety towards English language. But, a non significant difference or association was observed between different levels of anxiety and location of secondary schools towards English language (Chi-square=3.5191, $p > 0.05$) at 5% level of significance.

Findings of Correlation Analyses

1. The 9th standard students of secondary schools belonging to Ajara taluka have higher anxiety scores towards English language as compared to Budarghad taluka.

2. The 9th standard students of secondary schools belonging to Chandgad taluka have higher anxiety scores towards English language as compared to Budarghad taluka.
3. The 9th standard students of secondary schools belonging to Gadahinglaj taluka have higher anxiety scores towards English language as compared to Budarghad taluka.
4. The 9th standard students of secondary schools belonging to Karaveer taluka have higher anxiety scores towards English language as compared to Budarghad taluka.
5. The 9th standard students of secondary schools belonging to Karaveer taluka have higher anxiety scores towards English language as compared to Kagal taluka.
6. The girl students of secondary schools have higher anxiety scores about English language as compared to boys.
7. The rural and urban secondary schools students of 9th standard have similar anxiety scores about English language.
8. The 9th standard students of secondary schools belonging to Ajara taluka have higher anxiety scores towards English language as compared to Budarghad taluka students.
9. The 9th standard students of secondary schools belonging to Chandgad taluka have higher anxiety scores towards English language as compared to Budarghad taluka students.
10. The 9th standard students of secondary schools belonging to Karaveer taluka have higher anxiety scores towards English language as compared to Kagal taluka students.
11. The rural secondary school girl students of 9th standard of Ajara taluka have higher anxiety scores as compared to rural secondary school boy students of 9th standard of Budarghad taluka.
12. The rural secondary school girl students of 9th standard of Ajara taluka have higher anxiety scores as compared to urban secondary school boy students of 9th standard of Budarghad taluka.
13. The urban secondary school girl students of 9th standard of Ajara taluka have higher anxiety scores as compared to rural secondary school boy students of 9th standard of Budarghad taluka.
14. The urban secondary school girl students of 9th standard of Ajara taluka have higher anxiety scores as compared to urban secondary school boy students of 9th standard of Budarghad taluka.

Discussion and Conclusions

Researchers of foreign language education have investigated the effects of language anxiety on learning. Anxiety has been recognized as an important factor that influences the process learning English language, (Aida 1994, Macintyre and Gardner 1991). These studies showed some light on the role of anxiety in foreign language learning. They found that the college students of Japanese who were more anxious received significantly lower final grades than less anxious students. They also give some useful suggestions to reduce anxiety in the language classrooms.

This study found that a dual conceptualization of third language speaking anxiety as measured by the third language speaking anxiety scale was relevant to students studying English in Maharashtra. The results indicate that the instrument is reliable and valid and thus provides researchers with a new instrument to measure third language grammar, vocabulary and sentence pattern. It would be interesting to use this with third language learners of a lower linguistic level and also with students after they have started their university courses to investigate contextual influences on second language learning anxiety.

Implications of the Study

The findings of the present study have the following implications on the present context of India in which English language is treated as a third language.

1. The anxiety should be reduced to improve the level of English achievement among the High school students.
2. English should be taught in a stress free atmosphere. There should not be any fear for the learners in English language classrooms.
3. Remedial treatment is very much necessary to improve achievement level of students in English.
4. Bridge courses should be taken in schools to make them learn the third language effectively.
5. Teachers should be sensitive to the levels and needs of the third language learners.

Suggestions

1. The same study may be conducted using large sample of +2 stage.
2. A study like this may be under taken at state level as well as national level.
3. The same study may be conducted for the students studying in residential schools.

4. A study may be conducted at primary level.
5. A study may like this may be conducted by using higher order statistical techniques.

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